

CHANGES IN THE WATER LEVEL AND SALINITY OF THE EXPERIMENTAL FIELD

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Irrigation has dramatically changed the water balance of the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis, the desert region, and the districts of the Termiz group, which have been formed for centuries. As a result of water wastage through the walls and bottom of the canal, seepage through the soil during irrigation, the net part of the water balance has increased. Unfortunately, the predictions given by the designers regarding the rise of water in the newly irrigated massif of the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis did not come true. In practice, the rate of increase in the level of zahob exceeded that in the account book by 3-4 times. Because of this, there was an urgent need to build collective ditches and ditch networks.

Taking into account the moisture reserve in the soil, it is necessary that the water given in each irrigation does not exceed the moisture capacity of the soil, and as a result, we do not worsen the melioration condition of the irrigated soils by providing the soil with additional moisture.

Kiseleva I.K. (1963) noted that even though the level of soil salinization is superficial, less water than the norm according to the 0-2-0 or 1-1-0 system allows salinization of the plow layer of the soil.

The research conducted in the fields of the central experimental farm of UzPITI Surkhondarya branch in Termiz district. The data obtained on the level and salinity of the soil in 1999-2003-2005-2007-2010 are presented in tables 1, 2. Pre-sowing water applied in early spring (1200-1400 m³/ha) had the greatest effect on the Zahab level. As a result, the water level rose to 1.75-1.92 m.

It was observed that the soil level increases before each irrigation, and decreases after watering and gradually increases as the application period ends, due to the influence of the existing collective ditches and ditch systems, the increase in temperature during the application period, and the increase of evaporation from the surface of the earth. It was observed that the soil level after irrigation during the operation period increased mainly due to the amount of water supplied during this period and seasonal irrigation rates. In 3.8 options, the soil level before planting is 1.80-1.82 m. if there was, it increased from 1.57 m to 1.67 m after the pre-sowing water. During the operation period, before and after irrigation in these options, its level increased depending on the duration and rates of irrigation, and at the end of the operation period, it was close to the initial level. In options 3, 8, dry residue varied from 3.871 g/l to 4.088 g/l and chlorine ion from 0.471 g/l to 0.474 g/l. At the end of the application period, the level of salinity of the soil in both soil moisture systems slightly decreased, this happened due to the water supplied during the application period, and the amount of chlorine and ions in its content changed to 0.341-0.561 g/l and dry residue to 3.514-3.887 g/l. An increase in the level of moisture led to a decrease in the number of

irrigations, because cotton has the ability to absorb water with a salt content of 4 g/l, as many authors who conducted research in this field wrote.

Table 2

Soil salinity, before irrigation, g/l.

Optio	Name of salts	Water							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1.	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1999 year									
3.	dry residue	3,871	3,707	3,688	3,571	3,551	3,547		
	Chlorine ion	0,412	0,407	0,388	0,365	0,357	0,344		
8.	dry residue	4,088	3,887	3,811	3,787	3,755	3,708		
	Chlorine ion	0,474	0,469	0,460	0,451	0,427	0,411		
2000 year									
3.	dry residue	3,819	3,771	3,684	3,677	3,584	3,571	3,533	
	Chlorine ion	0,441	0,437	0,429	0,422	0,419	0,411	0,407	
8.	dry residue	4,057	4,031	3,832	3,829	3,787	3,771	3,614	
	Chlorine ion	0,461	0,457	0,451	0,429	0,417	0,411	0,409	
2001 year									
3.	dry residue	3,709	3,688	3,671	3,655	3,514			
	Chlorine ion	0,411	0,407	0,387	0,369	0,357			
8.	dry residue	3,666	3,622	3,608	3,579	3,561			
	Chlorine ion	0,387	0,369	0,357	0,351	0,341			

Conclusion

Our country - Southern region of Surkhan - Sherabad oasis, barren, barren, pale gray soils, underground water level 0.5-2.0 m, 2-3 m, 3.0 m deep (1999-2011) After that, laboratory, field, production experiments on the scientific basis and implementation of the system of irrigation and feeding systems, planting periods of cotton, winter wheat, and soybeans, seed consumption, thickness of seeds planted in the field, Termiz, Bandikhon, Kyziriq, Kumqshrgan, Sherabad, Muzrabot , Angor, Shorchi, Denov districts, we had to give conclusions and practical recommendations on the basis of many years of field and production experience in the conditions of the fields and fields.

References:

1. Avliyokulov A.E., Tsamutali A.S., Khusanov R.H., Bezborodov G.A. The system of agriculture in conditions of a fundamental change in the structure of agricultural production. Tashkent. A.O. " Agroindustry news ", 1998, 71 p.
2. Abraykulov A., Asamididinov A. Annual report of the regional department of agriculture and water management of the Surkhandarin region for 1997-1998, Termez 1998 P.1-7.

3. Abraykulov A., Asomiddinov A. Annual report of the Department of Agriculture and Water Management of Surkhandarya Region for 1997-2003. We sweat. 1997-2003. P.1-17.
4. Avliyakov A.E. Irrigation of crops of cotton crop rotation. Tashkent. Mehnat. 1988. 164 p.
5. Sullieva, S., & Zokirov, K. (2019). Biology of weeds. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 1(2), 120-124.
6. Boboeva, N. T., & Nazarov, S. U. The fight against avena fatua in the middle of a wheat field. International Journal on Integrated Education, 3(2), 62-64.
7. Суллиева, С. Х., & Зокиров, К. Г. (2020). Структура урожайности озимой пшеницы при применении гербицидов против сорняков. Экономика и социум, (9 (76)), 323-326.
8. Xurramovna, S. S., & Tuhtamishovna, B. N. Use Atlantis Herbicide for Avena Fatua in the Middle of a Wheat Field. International Journal on Integrated Education, 3(1), 45-47.
9. Суллиева, С. Х., & Зокиров, К. Г. (2020). Вредные свойства и классификация сорняков. Экономика и социум, (9 (76)), 319-322.
10. Sullieva, S. X., & G'Zokirov, Q. The Structure of the Yield of Winter Wheat When Using Herbicides Against Weeds. International Journal on Integrated Education, 3(11), 37-40.
11. Khurramovna, S. S., & O'G, Z. Q. G. A. (2021). Medicinal plants in folk medicine. European Scholar Journal, 2(3), 109-112.
12. Суллиева, С. Х., Бобоева, Н. Т., & Зокиров, К. Г. (2019). ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ЗЕМЛИ ВМЕСТЕ В ТЕКУЩЕМ ЛЕЧЕНИИ. Мировая наука, (6), 450-452.
13. Khurramovna, S. S. (2022). THE REACTION OF WATERMELON (CITRULLUS LANATUS (THUNB.) MATSUM. ET NAKAI.) TO ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS. Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development, 3, 99-102.
14. Sulliyeva, S., & Zokirov, Q. (2019). REPRODUCTION PLANTATIONS OF (HIPPOPHAE) IN SURHANDARYA REGION. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 1(2), 148-150.
15. Menglikulovich, A. S., Chutbaevich, B. K., & Habibullaevich, A. F. (2022). RESTORATION OF SEED FERTILITY IN ORDER TO RENEW THE SAMPLES OF VEGETABLE CROPS STORED IN THE GENE POOL. American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, 8, 91-95.
16. KHURRAMOVNA, S. (2020). TECHNOLOGY OF GROWING ZAFFARON IN THE SURHANDARYA AREA. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DISCOURSE ON INNOVATION, INTEGRATION AND EDUCATION, 1(5), 335-337.
17. Abdunazarov, E. E., & Zokirov, Q. (2019). PHYTOCHEMICAL INDICATORS OF MEDICINE PLANTS UNDER INTRODUCTION ON SALTED LANDS. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 1(5), 44-46.
18. Yakubjonovna, N. A., Chorievich, J. U., & Khasanova, M. (2022). PRODUCING, STORAGE AND PROCESSING OF MELONS USING MODERN RESOURCE-SAVING TECHNOLOGIES. American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, 10, 375-381.
19. Yakubjonovna, N. A., Chorievich, J. U., & Khasanova, M. (2022). Effect of Storage Methods and Periods on the Nutritional Properties of Watermelon. Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences, 10, 63-66.
20. Yakubjonovna, N. A., Chorievich, J. U., & Khasanova, M. (2022). Changes in yield and quality of melon dried fruit grown using different types of fertilization. Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences, 10, 67-70.

21. Khurramovna, S. S., & O'g, Z. Q. G. A. (2021). Economic efficiency of application of herbicides against double and double weeds in autumn wheat field.
22. Суллияева, С. Х., Бобоева, Н. Т., & Зокиров, К. Г. (2019). ВИДЫ И СОРТА ХРИЗАНТЕМ. Экономика и социум, (10 (65)), 315-317.

